

[研究文章 Research Article]

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Clarification of the Immature Stages of *Syntypistis viridipicta* (Wileman, 1910) (Lepidoptera, Notodontidae, Notodontinae, Stauropini)

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Abstract: The larval stage of *Syntypistis viridipicta* (Notodontidae; Wileman, 1910) is confirmed through eggs directly laid on host plants and subsequent adult voucher specimens. Previous misidentifications of this species with the morphologically similar species, *S. cyanea cyanea* (Leech, 1888), as well as their corresponding host plants, are clarified in this article.

Keywords: Oriental region, immature stage, hostplant, Styracaceae

Introduction

The notodontid moth genus *Syntypistis* Turner, 1907 is widely distributed from the Oriental to Indo-Australian regions and includes approximately 80 species. Larval host plants include the families Fagaceae, Styracaceae, Junglandaceae, and others (Schintlmeister, 2008). Ten species were previously recorded from Taiwan (Sugi, 1992), five of which have documented larval stages and host records (Shen, 1993; Lin & Shen, 1995). Wu et al. (2016) described a new species, *S. taipinshnensis* Wu & Hsu, 2016, with a specific host plant, *Fagus hayatae* (Fagaceae).

In Taiwan, *S. cyanea cyanea* (Leech, 1888) (type locality: Japan; figs 1, 2) and *S. viridipicta* (Wileman, 1910) (type locality: Taiwan; figs 3, 4) often co-occur and are sympatrically distributed in low to mid-elevation areas with very similar adult appearances. Although the final instar larvae of these two species illustrated by Shen (1993) and Lin & Shen (1996) show obvious differences in color and markings, the adult identifications in those publications are reversed (see discussion section), necessitating reconfirmation of the larval stage for these two species. This article partially clarifies the aforementioned issues using moth eggs laid on host plants in the wild and adult voucher specimens subsequently reared from the same host plants.

Material and methods

Four eggs on the ventral side of a mature leaf of *Styrax suberifolia* were collected from the peak of Mt. Xiochi (ca. 195 m a.s.l.) and placed in plastic containers measuring 14×14×25 cm. Three larvae subsequently hatched and continued to feed on the same host plant until pupation at the fifth instar. Pupae were kept in equally-sized containers and maintained in a moist environment using sphagnum moss until adult emergence. Living individuals were photographed using a Nikon Z30 digital camera and AF-S Micro Nikkor 60mm F2.8G ED lens with SB5000 flash covering SMDV Speedbox-Flip diffuser. Images were edited in Adobe Photoshop 2025 (Adobe Inc.).

Abbreviation

NTM National Taiwan Museum, Taipei

TFRI Insect collection, Taiwan Forestry Research Institute, Taipei

Results

Syntypistis viridipicta (Wileman, 1910) 綠脩舟蛾
(Figs 3, 4, 6–14)

Stauropus viridipicta Wileman, 1910, *Entomologist* 43: 312.

Stauropus chlorotricha Hampson, 1912, *J. Bombay Nat. Hist. Soc.*: 1271.

Quadricalcarifera marginalis Matsumura, 1925, *Zool. Mag., Tokyo*: 392; pl. 7: 6.

Quadricalcarifera kusukusuana Matsumura, 1929, *Insecta matsumurana*: 38; pl. 1: 15.

Quadricalcarifera medioviridis Kiriakoff, 1963, *Bonn. zool. Beitr.*: 263; photo 20; fig. 21.

Quadricalcarifera viridigutta Kiriakoff, 1963, *Bonn. zool. Beitr.*: 266; photo 24; fig. 25.

Quadricalcarifera dolaka Kiriakoff, 1967, *Lepidoptera Familia Notodontidae Pars secunda Genera Palaearctica*. In: P. Wytzman (ed.) *Genera Insectorum fasc. 217 B.*: 49, fig. 17.

Quadricalcarifera eusebia Kiriakoff, 1974, *Veröff. Zool. Staatssamml. Münch.*: 388; pl. 3: 1, 2; fig. 11.

Quadricalcarifera viridipicta: Nakatomi, 1987: 283, fig. 71: 14.

Syntypistis viridipicta: Schintlmeister, 2008: 16; Wang & Lu, 2012: 173, fig.; Kobayashi, 2020: 154, pl. 75: 15, 16, pl. 76: 1; Wu et al., 2021: 124, pl. 4: 17.

Specimens examined. TAIWAN. 1 male & 2 females, New Taipei City, Ruifang, Mt. Xiuchi, 195 m, 22. XII. 2024, leg. S. Wu, SWUBR2024-246, SWC2024-2074♂ & SWC2024-2075♀ & 2076♀ (NTM); 1 female, Taipei City, Jingmei, Sianjiyen, 27. XI. 2009, leg. S. Wu, TFRI00117692 (TFRI); 1 male, Ilan County, Fushan Botanical Garden, 27. XII. 2009, leg. S. Wu (TFRI); 1 male, ditto, 25. II. 2010, leg. S. Wu, TFRI117726; 1 male, ditto, 12. XI. 2010, leg. S. Wu (TFRI); 1 male, ditto, 10. IV. 2015, leg. S. Wu & W. C. Chang (TFRI); 1 female, Hualien Co., Jici, 8. II. 2019, leg. S. Wu, TFRI20490 (TFRI).

Diagnosis

In adults, *Sy. cyanea cyanea* is greyish and has less prominent forewing reniform and orbicular stigmata, while *Sy. viridipicta* is polymorphic (Schintlmeister, 2008) and has prominent forewing reniform and orbicular stigmata. The female of *Sy. viridipicta* has obvious forewing transversal black lines whereas the female of *Sy. cyanea cyanea* does not have these markings. In male genitalia, *Sy. viridipicta* (Fig. 6) can be easily distinguished from *Sy. cyanea cyanea* (Fig. 5) by the presence of a small projection on tegumen in the former but absence in the latter and the less curved phallus of the former, which is more curved in the latter.

Description of the immature stage

Shen (1993) and Lin & Shen (1995) illustrated the same final instar individual under the name *Sy. viridipicta* from Taiwan, but it is actually *Sy. cyanea cyanea*. Sugi (1987: pl. 71: 14) illustrated the second instar larva from Taiwan without hostplant information. Herein the re-description of larval and pupal stages are based on recently reared individuals.

Egg (Fig. 7, n=4) – Diameter approximately 1.2 mm; surface smooth, cream-white in early stage, transparent with pink first instar larval head visible inside during mature stage. 1st instar (Fig. 8, n=3, approximately 4 days) – Length approximately 4.7 mm in mature stage; head ochreous with two pairs of rufous spots, stemmata black; main ground coloration ochreous; tubercles light ochreous; dorsal parts of 2nd, 3rd thoracic segments and abdomen green; dorsolateral line white. 2nd instar (Fig. 9, n=3, approximately 4 days) – Length approximately 7.7 mm in mature stage; patterns similar to 1st instar but much more distinct. 3rd instar (Fig. 10, n=3, approximately 4 days) – Length approximately 15.4 mm in mature stage; ground coloration light yellowish green, dorsal part of 1st thoracic segment with one transversal black band; dorsal line from 2nd thoracic segment to end of abdomen light rufous. 4th instar (Fig. 11, n=3, approximately 5 days) – Length approximately 20.4 mm in mature stage; patterns similar to 3rd instar with upper region of spiracles red. Final instar (Fig. 12, n=3, approximately 7 days) – Length approximately 44.07 mm in mature stage (n=3; approximately 7 days); head ochreous, outer side of adfrontal suture tinged with dark brown; ground coloration light rufous with green tone; spiracles red; dorsal part of 1st thoracic segment with one black H-shaped pattern and outside yellow transversal band; dorsal line rufous; dorsal part of 10th abdominal segment with a narrowed black V-shaped band. Pupa (Fig. 13, 1 male and 2 females, 14 days) – length approximately 22 mm in male, 23 mm in females, ground coloration dark brown, smooth in appearance; epicranium blunt; antennae extending towards anterior third of forewing; spiracles black; cremaster present.

Distribution

Nepal, NE India, Myanmar, Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, China, Taiwan, Malayan Peninsula, and Sumatra (Schintlmeister, 2008).

Discussion

As mentioned in the introduction, the identifications of the illustrated adults of *Syntypistis cyanea cyanea* and *Sy. viridipicta* in Shen (1993) and Lin & Shen (1996) should be reversed. Therefore, their light brown mature larva fed with *Styrax subreifolia* should be identified as *Sy. viridipicta*, which fully matches with the information provided in the present study. Their light green mature larva with host plants *St. formosana* and *St. japonica* should be identified as *Sy. cyanea cyanea*. Wang & Lu (2012) correctly identified *Sy. viridipicta*, but the mentioned host plant “*St. formosanus*” was likely derived from the aforementioned misinterpreted information. According to the above information, the coloration of mature instar of *Sy. viridipicta* is light brown.

Nakatomi (1987) noted that the immature stages of *Sy. viridipicta* after the 2nd instar are unknown. Shen (1993) and Lin & Shen (1996) gave erroneous identifications for mature instars and adult stages of *Sy. viridipicta* as *Sy. cyanea*. The present study gives the information of all stages of *Sy. viridipicta*.

According to Kobayashi & Nonaka (2016), based on Taiwanese specimens the species *Sy. viridipicta* and *Sy. pryeri* (Leech, 1889) form a monophyletic group. The hostplants of the later species were confirmed as *Quercus acutissima* and *Q. japonica* by Nakatomi (1987), so host plant usage at the family level may not be conserved in this clade.

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綠胯舟蛾之幼生期釐清（鱗翅目：舟蛾科：舟蛾亞科：蟻舟蛾族）

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摘要:綠胯舟蛾 (*Syntypistis viridipicta*) 之幼生期於此研究透過產於寄主植物的卵與成蟲存證標本而被確認。過往本種與外觀近似之青苔胯舟 (*Sy. cyanea cyanea*) 蛾的誤鑑定在本研究中釐清，以及分別之寄主植物亦重新確認。

關鍵詞: 東方區、幼生期、寄主植物、安息香科

Figures 1–6. Habitus of *Syntypistis* of Taiwan. 1. *S. cyanea cyanea* (Leech, 1888), Fushan, Ilan County, male (TFRI); 2. Ditto, female, Fushan, Ilan County (TFRI); 3. *S. viridipicta* (Wileman, 1910), New Taipei City, Ruifang, male (SWC2024-2074, NTM); 4. Ditto, female (SWC2024-2074, NTM); 5. Male genitalia of *S. cyanea cyanea*, Fushan, Ilan County (TFRI); 6. Male genitalia of *S. viridipicta*, Fushan, Ilan County (TFRI). Scale bar for specimens= 10 mm. Photo by Shipher Wu.

Figures 7–14. Life stages of *Syntypistis viridipicta* (Wileman, 1910) in Mt. Xiuchi, Ruifang, New Taipei City, Taiwan. 7. Eggs; 8. 1st instar larva; 9. 2nd instar larva; 10. 3rd instar larva; 11. 4th instar larva; 12. Final instar larva; 13. Pupae, left male, right female; 14. Adults, left male (SWC2024-2074), right female (SWC2024-2075). Photo by Shipher Wu.